

IDENTIFYING GAPS FOR A COMPREHENSIVE LIFE CYCLE SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF BIO-BASED SECTORS IN EUROPE

State-of-the-art and results from a preliminary hotspot analysis

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INTRODUCTION

PROJECT PARTNERS

SECTORS

GOALS

- Realise a **state-of-the-art** of sustainability hotspots for the five bio-based sectors of CALIMERO (literature)
 - Environmental + Social + Economic
 - 3 sustainability pillars
- Identify **missing data** for materials and processes for Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment with current existing databases
- Identify **sustainability hotspots** with current methods
 - Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
 - Social LCA
 - Economic statistics (tentative method using Eurostats)

METHODS

Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment

RESULTS (EXCERPTS FROM WOODWORKING CASE STUDY)

- 49 billion EUR/year → 37k EUR/employee (2nd lowest of CALIMERO sectors)
- 1.3 million employees
- High concentration of value-added in Germany
- High location quotient in Baltic countries

- Survey results indicate highest risk for Workers (health & safety), communities (healthy living conditions), society (economic development), consumers (health & safety)
- Divergent indicators and results between PsiLCA and SHDB databases (results not depicted here)

WEBPAGE

www.calimeroproject.eu

- **Good coverage** of materials and transformation processes in ecoinvent and Gabi databases
- Only a few **missing species** for EU production (Larch, European Ash)
- **Regional specificity** could be improved

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